

Assess the Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on Knowledge of HPV Infection & Vaccination among Adolescent's Girls at Selected School in Greater Noida, UP

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Abstract:- Research with titled “Pre-experimental study to assess the effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on knowledge of HPV infection and vaccination among adolescent's girls at selected school in Greater Noida, UP”
METHODOLOGY: A Quantitative research approach was used and the pre-experimental one group pre-test and post-test research design was adopted for the present study. The target population for the study was adolescent girls, Sample size was 60. Sampling Technique for the study was Purposive Sampling Technique. **RESULTS:** In this research study that the majority of samples were 54[54.5%]in age group 13- 15 years , sample Pre-test finding of the study revealed that around 48.5% were having poor level of knowledge, about 12.1% of participants found with average level of knowledge and no one participants had good level of knowledge. Post-test finding of the study revealed that around 51.5% of them were having average level of knowledge; about 3.0% of them having good level of knowledge and 5.1% of them had poor level of knowledge. During Comparison of knowledge score of study reveals that, there was statistically significant difference noted in the mean knowledge scores of adolescents a girl regarding HPV Infection and Vaccination in pre-test and post-test($p < 0.005$). **Conclusion** It shows that the intervention was effective in improving the knowledge of adolescent's girls.

Keywords:- HPV Infection, Vaccination.

I. INTRODUCTION

The virus that causes cervical cancer (HPV) has been identified to be one of the main source of the vast majority of diseases transmitted through sexual contact that take place globally. For 99% of cancer of the cervical cavity cases around the globe, HPV is a widely recognized responsible a reason. At least 50% of sexually promiscuous men and women construct HPV in least once at their lifespan, says to data from CDC Prevention.(1)

One woman dies of cervical cancer (CC) every two minutes, making it one of the biggest risks to women's healthIt is currently the fourth most prevalent kind of malignancy in women globally, and annually, it claimed the existence of a large number of them, predominantly in countries with poor infrastructure. Human papillomavirus infection, among the most common illness transmitted through sexual contact (HPV), is one of the major risk factors for CC globally. Various health issues in both sexes, including further genital malignancies, could be brought on by this

➤ *Research Approach*

The focus of the research investigation is aimed at finding exactly how well-informed and conversant adolescent girls are in regards to HPV infection and vaccination especially within schools. In order to achieve the research goal, a quantitative research approach was deemed suitable.

➤ *Research Design*

Pre-experimental design one group pre and post-test design was selected to assess the efficiency of structured teaching programme on the prevalence of HPV infection and vaccination among teenage females in a particular Greater Noida school.

➤ *Variables*

• *Independent Variables*

The planned instruction approach on HPV infection and vaccination comprise the subject of the research's distinct factors.

• *Dependent Variables*

The factor that is dependent in the current investigation is knowledge concerning HPV infection and vaccination.

➤ *Research Setting*

The Study was conducted in Savitri Bai Phule Balika Inter College Greater Noida.

II. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The technique of categorizing, setting up, modifying, and aggregating up all of the data received during called analysis. The primary objective of statistical analysis is to extract facts into a comprehensible and accessible form so that the associations amongst each of the problem's components may be evaluated and validated.

➤ *Section 1*

Table 1. Respondent division by number and proportion in accordance with the preliminary test knowledge concerning being infected with HPV and vaccination.

Knowledge Level	Category Scores	Frequency	Percentage
Poor	< 8 score	48	48.5
Average	9-16 score	12	12.1
Good	>16 score	0	0
Total		60	60.6

The data presented in Table1 that nobody of the respondents showed a high level of understanding, only 12.1% had an average amount of information, and 48.5% had undesirable level of information.

Table 2 Respondent division by number and proportion in accordance with the post test knowledge concerning being infected with HPV and vaccination.

Knowledge Level	Category Scores	Frequency	Percentage
Poor	<8	5	5.1
Average	9-16	51	51.5
Good	>16	3	3.0
Total		59	59.6

The data presented in table 2 In terms of information, it was discovered that 51.5% of the respondents possessed a satisfactory level, 3.0% had an acceptable level, and 5.1% had a level that was low.

Table 3 Pre- and post-test comparison of adolescence girls' knowledge concerning HPV infection and vaccination.

Knowledge	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean Difference	Paired T-Test	P Value
Pre-test	5.29	2.182	6.22	15.89	.000
Post-test	11.51	2.381			

Table 3 reveals that The median knowledge ratings of adolescent females on HPV Infection and Vaccination revealed significantly distinct across pre-test and post-test at p.It demonstrates that the programme was beneficial in enhancing the understanding of young females. As a result, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis.

III. CONCLUSION

The key objective of the research project was to figure out how well the Structured Teaching Programme (STP) had instructed the teenage girls at Savitri Bai Phule Balika Inter College in Kasna, Greater Noida about HPV infection and vaccination.

It was discovered that it had a highly significant association between the outcomes of the pre- and post-tests and a few of the participants' socio-demographic factors (p 0.05).

The gathered data was tabulated, grouped and analyzed. Chi square tests were usedfor analysis. The following conclusions were drawn from the result of the study.

➤ *Nursing Practice*

The field of nursing has recently gone through certain transformations. The processes aimed at motivating persons to adopt safeguarding practises and maintain their wellness have been highlighted by a specialist nursing staff's widened oversight. Based to the investigation's the results, the vast majority of teenage girls achieved approximately average on a post-test on their knowledge about HPV infection and vaccination.

➤ *Nursing Research*

In the context of the outcomes, the investigator is able to conduct out further studies with a bigger sample size in various contexts for the goal of applicability. Research investigations can be carried out for the assessment of getting immunised and infection knowledge of working women and teenagers.

➤ *Nursing Education*

The curriculum should include and teach students how to stay healthy and prevent various health problems . Teacher should encourage and counsel the students regarding vaccination. Educate students about inculcate about infection and vaccination according to their age.

➤ *Nursing Administration*

The teenage girls in the educational institution have to receive the necessary training in nursing regarding HPV Infection and Vaccination. Teenager girls' comprehension of HPV infection and vaccination can be upgraded through training sessions, shows, conferences, and drawing competitions.

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